

Vacancy Promotion in Layered Double Hydroxide Electrocatalysts for Improved Oxygen Evolution Reaction Performance.

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KEYWORDS: *Oxygen evolution reaction, Oxygen vacancies, Layered double hydroxide, in-situ XAS electrocatalytic model, density functional theory*

ABSTRACT: Layered double hydroxides (LDHs) are promising catalysts for the oxygen evolution reaction (OER) given their modular chemistry and ease of synthesis. Herein, we report on a facile strategy for inclusion of oxygen vacancies (V_o) using Ce as a promoter in Co-Ni LDHs that significantly enhances the activity for OER. In-situ X-ray absorption spectroscopy (XAS) uncovers an increase in octahedral Co sites and V_o upon addition of Ce that promotes the transformation of the LDH into the oxyhydroxide reactive phase more readily. The presence of OER active oxyhydroxide phase along with the generation of V_o facilitated by the partial reduction of Ce^{4+} to Ce^{3+} under oxidizing conditions results in a better electrochemical activity of Ce doped electrocatalysts. Density functional theory (DFT) further corroborates in-situ XAS experimental findings by showcasing that presence of both Ce and V_o reduces the free-energy barrier of rate limiting OH^* deprotonation step during OER. This work showcases how an enhanced understanding of the role of V_o promoters in LDHs electrocatalysts can provide insights for future catalyst design in anodic reactions.

Introduction

Electrochemical water splitting is the preeminent technology to access carbon-neutral green hydrogen for future use as fuels and chemical reagents. The technology is significantly hindered by the anodic oxygen evolution reaction (OER), which often occurs at a large overpotential with poor reaction kinetics.¹⁻³ Much effort has been focused on alkaline OER, where catalyst consisting of first row transition metals can often outperform commercially implemented catalysts consisting of platinum group metals.⁴⁻⁸ Among the reported transition metal based electrocatalysts, layered double hydroxides (LDHs) are especially promising for OER, as the ability to modulate metal chemistries within a 2D hydroxide lattice allows for optimized structure and electronics, often with some of the best alkaline OER

performance reported to date.⁹⁻¹⁶ The most common LDHs for OER employ a base structure of M^{2+}/M^{3+} hydroxides using Co, Fe, and/or Ni, where OER performance can be improved with the inclusion of high valency metal dopants,¹⁷⁻¹⁹ modulation of the interlayer spacing/anion chemistry,²⁰⁻²² and heterostructuring onto various substrates (e.g., graphene, carbon nanotubes).²³⁻²⁵ Though relatively understudied, the directed incorporation of oxygen vacancies (V_o) have also shown the ability to greatly improve OER overpotentials due to the improved charge transfer and providing electrophilic sites to attract nucleophilic species like OH^- .²⁶⁻³⁰ From a fundamental perspective, the precise role of V_o in OER is not well elucidated in LDHs, leading to a lack of atomic-scale insights needed for further electrocatalyst development for OER.

In this contribution, we describe a methodology for engineering V_0 into a model Co-Ni LDH using Ce as a vacancy-promoting dopant metal. An optimization of Ce concentration leads to an electrocatalyst with ~ 70 mV reduction in overpotential at 10 mA/cm^2 as compared to the unmodified Co-Ni LDH and 100% Faradaic efficiency (FE) to O_2 . Furthermore, the Ce-doped Co-Ni LDH exhibits improved charge transfer kinetics and desirable stability, with electrolyzers implementing anodes made with 5% Ce-doped Co-Ni LDH performing favourably in comparison to analogous devices using IrO_2 at the anode. The atomic scale origins of the enhanced reactivity were then thoroughly studied using suite of atomic-scale characterization tools and computational approaches. In particular, in-situ X-ray absorption spectroscopy (XAS) measurements reveal a promotion of octahedral Co sites at lower potentials due to the presence of Ce-induced V_0 , wherein Ce facilitates this transformation through a partial in-situ reduction from Ce^{4+} to Ce^{3+} at the same overpotentials.

Further density functional theory calculations add insight to our in-situ XAS observations and further depicts improved reaction energetics for OER for Co-oxyhydroxides due to V_0 and the local presence of Ce dopants. Taken together, our work not only demonstrates the ease of V_0 generation through Ce doping but provides insights into the manipulation/optimization of local structure through V_0 needed to guide future LDH development for OER and other potential electrooxidation reactions.

Results

Electrochemical Performance

The effect of Ce doping on OER was investigated on a series of Co-Ni-Ce LDHs prepared using established co-precipitation methods (see Methods section).³¹ Co-Ni LDHs were chosen as a model LDH system given its established OER performance and well understood catalytic mechanisms and structural transformation.^{12-14,16}

Note that Ce doping percentage is given relative to the Co sites, where the concentration of Ni is maintained in all catalysts. The electrocatalytic performance of the LDH materials was first probed using linear sweep voltammetry (LSV) measurements (Figure 1a). Before the onset of OER, redox peaks corresponding to $\text{Co}^{2+}/\text{Co}^{3+}$ and $\text{Ni}^{2+}/\text{Ni}^{3+}$ transitions associated with the formations of oxyhydroxides³² are the most notable for LDHs doped with 5% and 10% Ce, showcasing the influence of Ce doping on converting the LDH into its active state. Moreover, oxidation and reduction peaks are nearly symmetric for all LDH materials, indicative of reversibility of Co/Ni redox states, as shown in cyclic voltammetry (Figure S1). At 10 mA cm^{-2} , Ce-doped electrocatalysts show lower overpotentials compared to the undoped Co-Ni LDH (Figure 1 a, b), with a maximum improvement of ~ 70 mV in 5% Ce doped LDH vs Co-Ni LDH. At 1% and 10% Ce doping, lower overpotentials are still obtained vs Co-Ni LDH

(380 and 395 mV respectively), but notably higher than 5% Ce, indicating that a balance of Ce is needed to improve OER. As controls, Ce-Co and Ce-Ni LDHs were evaluated where Ce completely replaced either Ni or Co atoms, leading to LDHs with higher overpotentials than Co-Ni LDH at 10 mA cm^{-2} . Ce-Co LDH has especially poor performance, showcasing the need for Ni and the lack of direct OER reactivity with Ce. Further, we also performed electrochemical active surface area (ECSA) measurements, the obtained intrinsic electrocatalyst activities are consistent with the trend observed in geometrical current densities as depicted in Figure 1a (see SI Note 1).

Figure 1. Electrochemical performance of Ce-Co-Ni LDH electrocatalysts. a, LSV of LDHs on glassy carbon working electrode measured with a 5 mV.s^{-1} scan rate, without iR correction in 1 M KOH solution at ambient temperature. b, Overpotentials ($\eta = E - 1.23\text{V}$) obtained at current density 10 mA cm^{-2} . c, Tafel plots of Co-Ni LDH and Ce doped electrocatalysts. d, Chronopotentiometric curves for Co-Ni and 5% Ce doped LDHs at 10 mA cm^{-2} in 1 M KOH at ambient temperature. e, Comparison of DEMS and electrochemical measurements. f, 5% Ce doped electrocatalyst comparison with IrO_2 catalyst.

The kinetics of prepared LDHs was assessed through Tafel plots derived from LSV curves. As shown in Figure 1c, the resultant Tafel slope of 5% Ce doped (130 mV dec^{-1}) is much smaller than those of 1% Ce doped (178 mV dec^{-1}), 10% Ce doped (167 mV dec^{-1}) and Co-Ni LDH (221 mV dec^{-1}), demonstrating fast OER kinetics for 5% Ce doped sample.

Figure 2. Structural characterization of Ce-Co-Ni LDHs. a, STEM image and b, c, d, EDX maps of Co, Ni and Ce in 5% Ce doped Co-Ni LDH, respectively. e, Atomic PDFs of doped and undoped LDHs. (f-h) XANES spectra of as synthesized LDHs for f, Ni K-edge g, Co K-edge h, Ce L_{3} -edge (dash and dotted lines represent the corresponding metal foils and standards). (i-j) Ex-situ magnitudes of the Fourier-transformed EXAFS spectra for i, Ni K-edge. j, Co K-edge. k, Ex-situ NEXAFS spectra for oxygen K-edge.

Further, we carried out electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) analysis at 1.62 V vs RHE (SI Note 2 and Figures S2-S4). The equivalent circuit fitting results (Table S1) showcase 5% Ce doped exhibits a smaller Faradic resistance as compared to other LDHs. These EIS results indicate higher charge transfer kinetics along with the ease of relaxing adsorbed intermediate species during OER and is consistent with the observed Tafel kinetics. Constant current chronopotentiometry tests (Figure 1d) were performed at 10 mA.cm⁻² for Co-Ni LDH and 5% Ce doped samples, both LDH materials showed remarkable lab-scale stability. Moreover, electrochemical performance results showcase Ce doping not only improves charge transfer kinetics

but may trigger favourable surface reaction mechanism due to the presumed presence of V_{0} defects, as elucidated below. Differential electrochemical mass spectrometry (DEMS) measurements (Figure 1e) were conducted to obtain the Faradaic efficiencies (FE) of Ce doped and pristine Co-Ni LDH. 5% Ce doped LDH achieved ~100% FE towards OER, while Co-Ni LDH achieved ~ 87% FE. The higher FE in 5% Ce doped LDH could be attributed to V_{0} defects which help to increase the electron transferability between catalyst surface and adsorbates due to the presence of localized extra electrons in the defect sites.³³ Based on the results of the DEMS measurements, 5% Ce doped was used for

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electrolyzer measurements. A comparison with Ir-based catalyst³⁴ is shown in Figure 1f, showcases that the LDH system has excellent electrochemical performance comparable to those of precious metal-based systems, especially when considering comparative catalysts cost. Additional experimentation and performance characteristics of the electrolysis experiments can be found in the SI Notes 3-5.

Materials Characterization

To better understand the role of Ce dopants during OER reaction, the electrocatalysts were thoroughly characterized using a range of electron microscopy and synchrotron techniques. The size and morphology of the prepared Ce-doped LDHs were investigated by scanning transmission electron microscopy (STEM) as shown in Figure 2a and Figure S10. The stacked 2D nanosheets were observed for 5% Ce, which is consistent with undoped Co-Ni LDH here and reported elsewhere.^{16,35} The lateral dimension of the LDHs ranged from ~30 to ~400 nm, with the variable contrast from the STEM images is likely attributed to the stacking of LDHs. Atomic force microscopy (AFM) images and profilometry (Figure S11-12) of the LDHs yield thickness from 10-20 nm for both doped and undoped materials, illustrating that Ce does not appreciably change LDH morphology. Energy dispersive X-ray (EDX) mapping in STEM mode of the 5% Ce doped LDH is shown in Figure 2 (b, c, d) and showcases a uniform distribution of Ce in the LDH sheets. ICP OES results (Table S3) compliments the EDX spectrum (Figure S9), further confirming the stoichiometry of as prepared doped LDHs. UV-Visible spectroscopy (Figure S13) revealed the presence of both tetrahedral and octahedral configurations within Co-Ni LDH, and tetrahedral character reduced upon Ce doping. The absorption bands of octahedral Ni²⁺ and Co²⁺ in UV spectra of doped and undoped samples are poorly recognized due to low absorption coefficients and enhanced center of symmetry as compared to Co²⁺ tetrahedral configuration. Other advanced characterization techniques such as XAS are required to elucidate the local structure of prepared LDHs (SI Note 6). The presence of tetrahedral character in Co-Ni LDH suggests vacant Co²⁺ octahedral sites are more likely to be occupied by the pair of tetrahedral metal centres as reported in other studies.^{36,37}

We further characterized the LDH electrocatalysts using high energy X-ray diffraction (HE-XRD). The resulting diffraction patterns (Figure S14) were converted into reduced structure functions ($F(Q)$) and Fourier transformed into atomic pair distribution functions (PDFs)³⁸ providing structural insights in terms of atomic pair distances within the LDH nanosheets (Figure 2e). The profiles of the PDFs for undoped and doped samples are similar and long-range ordering has been observed, indicating again that the inclusion of Ce does not drastically change the local structure of the LDHs. The intensity of peak at ~3.80 Å increases with Ce doping suggests preferable Ce sites in LDH (See SI Note 7). These characterisation techniques reveal that Ce only influences the local coordination environment by promoting octahedral configuration while overall morphology remains identical in doped and undoped LDHs.

To investigate the local chemistry and structure of pristine doped and undoped LDHs, we performed X-ray absorption

spectroscopy (XAS). The X-ray absorption near edge structure (XANES) spectra for Ni K-edge, Co K-edge along with the reference metal foils and bulk compounds are shown in Figure 2 (f, g). Ni K-edge XANES spectra show no detectable differences in undoped and doped samples compared to Ni(OH)₂ standard, suggesting Ni maintains octahedral geometry with oxidation state Ni²⁺ (Figure 2f). Contrary to Ni K-edge, profound changes could be seen in the Co K-edge XANES (Figure 2g), which changes to both pre-edge features and the white line intensity. We observe that undoped Co-Ni LDH shows the strongest intensity of the pre-edge peak and then decreases with Ce doping. This indicates a reduction of the Co-O₄ tetrahedron sites and relative increase of the Co-O₆ octahedrons³⁹ as tetrahedral coordinated 3d metal ions have more intense pre-edge peaks due to the local mixing of 3d and 4p states, inferring combined 1s 3d quadrupole and 1s 4p dipole transitions.⁴⁰ The increase in white line intensity of Co K-edge XANES in Ce doped samples is attributed to more octahedral character along with the increased unoccupied d states in Co ions, likely contributed by vacancy formation with the inclusion of Ce. Additionally, Ce L₃-edge XANES for doped LDHs together with Ce(NO₃)₃·6H₂O and CeO₂ standards are depicted in Figure 2h. A single intense peak in Ce(NO₃)₃·6H₂O standard is attributed to the excitation of an electron from Ce 2p_{3/2} state to 4f¹5d state, where two peaks in CeO₂ are assigned to electronic transition from Ce 2p_{3/2} to of 4f¹5d¹ and 4f⁰5d¹ final states.^{41,42} The Ce L₃-edge XANES spectra show noticeable changes in edge position and white line intensity features (Figure 2h) in doped samples. The reduction in white line intensity and edge energy position shift to higher energy with increased Ce loading shows Ce was predominantly oxidized to Ce⁴⁺. Extended X-ray absorption fine structure (EXAFS) analysis for Co and Ni K-edges XAS are shown in Figure 2 (i-j). The EXAFS fits are depicted in Figure S25-S32, and modelling results are mentioned in Tables S4-S5. The Ni K-edge EXAFS modelling results indicate Ni-O and Ni-M distances and coordination numbers (CNs) do not appreciably change with Ce doping. While in Co K-edge EXAFS, although the peak locations for Co-O and Co-M are similar to octahedral Co(OH)₂ standard the relative intensity of these peaks is significantly reduced in undoped Co-Ni LDH. The EXAFS modelling results reveal reduced average CN in undoped sample suggests presence of Co-tetrahedral and Co-octahedral configurations in the LDH structure because average CNs reduced from six with the existence of both four and six coordinated Co ligands. In contrast to undoped sample, we observed increased intensities of first shell Co-O and Co-M in Ce doped samples suggesting higher coordination environment close to octahedral Co(OH)₂ (Table S5).

In addition, we also performed XAS in the soft X-ray regime to probe metal L-edge chemistry and the near edge X-ray absorption spectra (NEXAFS) of O and N K-edges. Consistent with K-edge XANES, Ni was present in Ni²⁺ while Co in a mixed octahedral-tetrahedral Co²⁺ and subtle Co³⁺ also present in doped LDHs (Figure S17).⁴³⁻⁴⁵ Additionally, NEXAFS at the N K-edge (Figure S17) reveals typical features of NO₃⁻⁴⁶ in LDH interlayers, the white line intensity increases upon addition of more positive Ce is likely to

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Figure 3. Structural evolution of Ce doped Co-Ni LDHs during OER. a-e In-situ XANES spectra of a, Co-Ni LDH for Ni K-edge. b, 5% Ce doped for Ni K-edge. c, Co-Ni LDH for Co K-edge. d, 5% Ce doped for Co K-edge. e, 5% Ce doped for Ce L₃-edge. f, Edge energy changes with applied potential, blue Co K-edge and green Ni K-edge.

influence the concentration and covalency of nitrate anions within interlayers to keep the charge balance in LDHs.⁴⁷ The N K-edge (Figure S 17) reveals pronounced NO₃⁻ anions concentration in 10% Ce doped followed by 1% and 5% Ce doped samples. The favourable V₀ formation in 5% Ce doped causes less NO₃⁻ within LDH interlayer to compensate charge as compared to other doped samples. O K-edge NEXAFS (Figure 2k) spectra shows three noteworthy features: a main peak (a) ~530.5 eV due to the O(1s) to O(2p) orbitals mixed with Co(3d)t_{2g} or Ni(3d)t_{2g}, a small peak (b) at ~531.8 eV represents O(π*) of NO₃⁻ and peak (c) ~533.2 eV is related to oxygen bound to hydroxyl species while spectral intensities between 535 eV and 545 eV describe dominant near edge transitions from the water molecules present in the interlayers of LDH.^{46,48} The appearance of shoulder peak before peak (a) at ~529 eV in 5 and 10% Ce doped sample suggests electronic transitions between O (2P) states mixed with Ce 4f states.⁴⁹ The intense shoulder peak in 10% Ce doped sample indicates more unoccupied states at O (2p) mixed with Ce (4f).^{28,50} It is to be noted that the shoulder peak ~529 eV could also be the indication of O ligand redox activity. These electrophilic O ligands were found to be the active sites for OER on surface of various oxides such as Ir, Ru, and NiFe LDH as reported elsewhere.⁵¹⁻⁵³ The intensity of peak (a) is related to the unoccupied electronic states in O (2P). The unoccupied states in O (2p) hybridized with Co/Ni (3d) increases when replacing Co with Ce. The 10% Ce doped sample should reflect highest peak (a) intensity, but we observed 5% Ce doped sample has highest intensity (Inset Figure 2k). The higher intensity of peak (a) in 5% Ce doped sample indicates increased

unoccupied states in O(2P) due to the favourable V₀ formation, which resulted in improved OER performance.

Local structural changes and role of Ce doping during OER

To monitor local structural changes during OER, we performed in-situ XAS experiments under the OER-relevant conditions. During the in-situ XAS experiments, the applied potential was increased from open circuit voltage (OCV) to 1.22, 1.32, 1.52 and 1.62 V vs RHE and XAS spectra for Co, Ni K-edges, and Ce L₃-edge were recorded at each potential after reaching the stable state, as shown Figure 3 and Figure S18. Ni K-edge XANES for Co-Ni LDH and 5% Ce doped LDH under applied bias is shown in Figure 3(a-b) while data for 1 and 10% Ce doped samples are shown in Figure S18. A similar trend could be seen in the Ni K-edge energy position E₀ for doped and undoped samples (Figure 3f), which moves to higher energies as potential increases, indicating the oxidation of Ni²⁺ at OCV and 1.22 V to Ni^{3+/4+} at 1.32, 1.52 and 1.62 V, also observed elsewhere for Ni-based catalysts.^{6,17,54} The in-situ XANES results suggest Ni is less prone to Ce doping, likely due to doping replacement in the materials (Ce for Co) and the increased relative concentration of Co to Ni (~3x). The in-situ XANES of Co K-edge for Co-Ni LDH and 5% Ce doped is shown in Figure 3(c-d) while 1 and 10% Ce doped Co K-edge XANES are depicted in Figure S18. Contrary to Ni K-edge XANES, we observed more pre-edge energy position shift in doped LDHs as compared to undoped LDH. The same trend could be seen in the relative pre-edge peak intensities where doped LDH exhibit higher peak

Figure 4. Local structural changes in Ce doped and undoped LDHs. a, Fourier-transformed Co K-edge EXAFS spectra for Co-Ni LDH at OCV, 5% Ce doped at OCV, Co-Ni LDH and 5% Ce doped at 1.62 V vs RHE. b-e, WT analysis of the Co K-edge EXAFS spectra of Co-Ni LDH and 5% Ce doped (b), Co-Ni LDH at OCV (c) 5% Ce doped at OCV, (d), Co-Ni LDH at 1.62V (e), 5% Ce doped at 1.62V. f, CNs for Co-O and Co-M obtained from Co K-edge EXAFS modelling of Co-Ni LDH at various potentials starting from OCV=0.91 V vs RHE. g, CNs for Co-O and Co-M obtained from Co K-edge EXAFS modelling of 5% Ce doped sample.

intensities. These observations suggest that Ce doped electrocatalysts transform into more distorted structures under increased potential as compared to undoped samples. Further, doped LDHs show increased shift in E_0 to higher energy as opposed to undoped LDHs (Figure 3f), which reveals higher fraction of Co²⁺ ions were oxidized to valence states Co^{3+/4+} in the doped sample. Similar features could be seen in 1 and 10% Ce doped Co K-edge XANES (Figure S18). The more distorted Co octahedral structure in doped LDHs indicates the existence of high valence Co^{3+/4+} ions and presence of V_0 near Co atoms due to Ce doping. Further, the Ce L₃-edge XANES spectra for 5% Ce doped along with the reference Ce(NO₃)₃·6H₂O and CeO₂ is shown in Figure 3e and for 1 and 10% Ce doped in Figure S18. The XANES spectrum of 5% Ce doped sample exhibits a visible shift to lower energies by increasing potential and a shoulder peak appears at 5727.5 eV which corresponds to Ce³⁺. These observations suggest the reduction of Ce⁴⁺ to Ce³⁺ due to the formation of V_0 at OER potentials.⁵⁵ A similar but less noticeable feature can also be seen in 1 and 10% Ce doped samples (Figure

S18) where shoulder peak is not as pronounced as in 5% Ce doped LDH, which suggests less V_0 in 1 and 10% Ce doped samples at OER potentials. The reduced V_0 formation in 1% doped Ce is likely attributed to the doping concentration available to undergo reduction and subsequent V_0 generation. The excessive Ce in 10% doped material triggers mixing of more O (2p) states with Ce (4f), as shown in O K-edge NEXAFS (Figure 2k) which reduces V_0 formation. These findings suggest that optimum Ce concentration is critical to enhance electrocatalytic performance.⁵⁶ The optimal 5% Ce content in doped LDH lattice generates favourable V_0 to provide additional electrophilic sites for OH⁻ adsorption during OER, thus enhanced electrochemical performance. The Ce³⁺ ↔ Ce⁴⁺ redox transformation induces the generation of V_0 , thus ensuring good electron transport due to highly mobile lattice oxygen. In addition, high electron affinity of Ce⁴⁺ could attract partial electrons from nearby Co active sites resulting in a higher electron affinity at the Co sites to promote rate limiting OH⁻ deprotonation. To assess the assumption of local structure change for Co/Ni due to

Figure 5. DFT calculation on Ce and V₀ incorporation into Co-Ni LDH and their OER reactivity. a, Structural models of Co(OH)₂ configurations to compute free energy of hydroxide to oxyhydroxide transformation. The Ce, Co, O and H atoms are represented by green, dark blue, red and pinkish-white spheres, respectively. The oxygen vacancy is highlighted by a dotted red circle. b, DFT computed free energy diagram for hydroxide to oxyhydroxide conversion c, Structural model for Ce-CoOOH V₀ unit cell. d, Surface structures showing the four different intermediates. The Ce, Co, O, K and H atoms are represented by green, dark blue, red, purple, and pinkish-white spheres, respectively. The oxygen vacancy and the active site are highlighted by dotted red and dotted blue circles, respectively. e, Free energy diagram for OER key steps.

the presence of Ce and V₀, we performed wavelet transformation (WT) analysis (See Methods and SI Note 8) on Co and Ni K-edge EXAFS spectra to determine the neighbouring atoms around the absorbing metal center. WT analysis reveal Ni is less affected by Ce doping (Figure S24), consistent with the in-situ Ni K-edge XANES analysis. Contrary to Ni K-edge, the high valence phase Co^{3+/4+} is more noticeable in 5% Ce doped LDH (Figure 4e) comparing with undoped sample (Figure 4d) indicating the synergistic role of Ce and V₀ in doped LDH for OER. The WT analysis is consistent with the peaks observed in R space, Figure 4a (See SI Note 9). To get quantitative local structure, EXAFS modelling was performed for Co and Ni EXAFS (See Methods). The EXAFS modelling results (Table S10-S13) for Ni K-edge are consistent with in-situ XANES analysis and mostly unchanged with Ce doping fall within the error bars of the EXAFS modelling (See SI Note 10). The k₂-weighted Co K-edge EXAFS modelling obtained results are presented in Tables S6-S9, EXAFS fits in Figure S25-S28. All samples exhibit a broad Co-O peak that accounts for both Co²⁺-O and Co^{3+/4+}-O and two metal shells representing Co²⁺ and Co^{3+/4+} as shown in Figure 4a and WT analysis Figure (b-e). To

compare doped and undoped Co k-edge EXAFS modelling results, we illustrate Co-Ni LDH and 5% Ce doped obtained CNs, Figure 4 (f-g). A strong oxidation of the initial present Co²⁺ ions to Co^{3+/4+} ions within the Co-Ni-Ce LDHs is manifested in the shift of the CNs for Co-O and Co-M for doped and undoped LDHs. It is to be noted that subtle Co³⁺ phase exists at OCV which is more noticeable in 5% Ce doped as compared to undoped sample, where the CN of Co³⁺ phase increases while CN decreases for Co²⁺ phase with applied potential suggests formation of oxyhydroxide phase.

The combined Co-O CN is close to ~6 for Co-Ni LDH at OCV and 1.62 V while CN decreases to ~4 at OCV and further decreased to ~3 at 1.62 V for 5% Ce doped sample suggests oxygen deficiency in 5% Ce doped sample due to Ce doping influenced V₀ formation, also reported in similar studies to determine V₀ with EXAFS.⁵⁷⁻⁵⁹ The transformation of Co²⁺ into reactive phase in doped LDH is attributed to the Ce doping and presence of V₀. This reactive Co-oxyhydroxide phase is the most favourable configuration to catalyse OER due to the formation of OOH*.⁶⁰ In addition to the presence of active oxyhydroxide phase, V₀ may help to increase the

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electron transport between catalyst surface and adsorbates due to the presence of localized extra electrons.

To investigate structural changes induced by oxidative OER processing, we performed surface sensitive XAS at Co and Ni L-edges (Figure S37) on electrodes obtained after 30 CVs at scan rate 20 mV.s⁻¹, followed by chronoamperometry by holding fixed OER potential 1.62 V vs RHE for 2 hours. We observed pronounced changes in Ni and Co local structures after extended OER processing which are consistent in doped and undoped samples. The NEXAFS spectra at Co and Ni L₂/L₃-edges for electrodes after OER confirm presence of higher oxidation Co³⁺ and Ni³⁺ phases. This observation establishes the irreversible valence change of Ni and Co during the oxygen evolution reaction. The irreversible conversion of Co(OH)₂ into amorphous high valence CoOOH phase is well established in other studies.⁶¹⁻⁶³ However, there is limited understanding about stabilization of high valence NiOOH phase after OER processing. Cai et al.⁶⁴ observed formation and stabilization of NiOOH in LDH due to the presence of FeOOH and dynamic phase restructuring induced by electro-oxidation.

Density functional theory calculations

Our in-situ XAS experiments revealed the presence of Ce-induced V₀ result in an easier transition from the OER inactive hydroxide phase to the active oxyhydroxide phase. This is evidenced by the oxidation of Co sites at lower potentials in the presence of Ce. We use density functional theory (DFT) calculations to test if V₀ and Ce indeed play a favourable role in making this transition easier. DFT calculations were conducted on brucite layered Co(OH)₂ structure. We assessed the free energy of the oxidation reaction, i.e. from Co(OH)₂ to CoOOH by removing a H atom from the Co(OH)₂ structure. We assessed this reaction on four different surfaces: pristine Co(OH)₂, Ce-doped Co(OH)₂, V₀-Co(OH)₂ and Ce-doped V₀-Co(OH)₂ (Figure 5a). Our results, presented in Figure 5b, show that the presence of both Ce and the V₀ decrease the free energy of this transition, i.e. from a value of -0.24 eV on Co(OH)₂ to values of -1.44, -0.36 and -1.39 eV on Ce-Co(OH)₂, V₀-Co(OH)₂ and Ce-V₀-Co(OH)₂, respectively. This shows the positive impact of V₀ and Ce doping on OER, consistent with our experiments. Further, we conducted DFT to understand the impact of V₀ on the OER performance in undoped and Ce-doped samples, the DFT calculations were conducted on the (10 $\bar{1}$ 0) surface of γ -CoOOH. We modeled the OER mechanism as follows:

First, we assessed the OER pathway on pristine CoOOH and Ce-doped CoOOH (Ce-CoOOH), i.e. structures containing no oxygen vacancies (see Figure 5 c,d). Consistent with previous calculations,^{7,43} we found that the OH* deprotonation step is the rate-limiting step and presents the highest reaction barrier for the OER pathway. The reaction free energy

barriers for CoOOH and Ce-CoOOH were computed to be 2.19 and 2.15 eV, respectively (see inset of Figure 5e). We then assessed the OER pathway on CoOOH with an oxygen vacancy (CoOOH V₀) and Ce-doped CoOOH with an oxygen vacancy (Ce-CoOOH V₀), i.e. structures containing oxygen vacancies and compared the obtained results with the cases with no oxygen vacancies. We found that the OH* deprotonation step is still the rate-limiting step, however, interestingly, the free energy barrier associated with this step is reduced (1.97 and 1.81 eV for CoOOH V₀ and Ce-CoOOH V₀, respectively) compared to the cases with no oxygen vacancies. Thus, we found that the presence of oxygen vacancies can favourably affect the OER performance as observed in our in-situ XAS experiments. To obtain more insights, we carried out Bader analysis on all the catalyst structures. In CoOOH, we found that the active Co site has an oxidation state of +1.32. In the presence of Ce, the active Co site in Ce-CoOOH received additional electrons and was found to have an oxidation state of +1.29. Following a similar trend, the presence of oxygen vacancies further reduced the active Co site resulting in an oxidation state of +1.11 and +1.06 in CoOOH-V₀ and Ce-CoOOH-V₀ structures, resembling. These results align well with our free energy findings, in that it can be noticed that the presence of additional electrons on the active Co site stabilizes both OH* and O* (more O* than OH*) intermediates, thereby reducing the barrier for the OH* deprotonation step. As such, the presence of oxygen vacancies and Ce dopants can make OER favourable.

Conclusions

In this work, we endeavoured to address the limiting anodic reaction in water splitting through defect engineering of transition metal based LDHs. We demonstrated facile synthesis of defects enriched Ce doped Co-Ni LDHs, which achieved ~70 mV less overpotential through optimal Ce doping in host Co-Ni LDH. The 5% Ce doped Co-Ni LDH realized 100 % FE, higher than that of bare Co-Ni LDH and comparable large-scale performance with commercially used IrO₂ electrocatalyst as reported in benchmark study³⁴. We also obtained remarkable stability of prepared electrocatalysts. The atomic scale model guided by in-situ XAS and DFT revealed improved OER performance in Ce doped electrocatalysts. The reversible Ce³⁺ ↔ Ce⁴⁺ redox transformation induces the generation of V₀ during OER hence better electrochemical performance. This work not only opened new avenues to design defect-engineered electrocatalysts for OER but also offered new opportunities for other electrooxidation reactions.

Methods and Experimental Section

Synthesis of Ce doped Co-Ni LDH

Co-Ni based LDHs were synthesized by co-precipitation method. The host Co-Ni LDH structure was modified by selective doping of Ce ions. First, 1.5 mmol Co²⁺ (Cobalt nitrate hexahydrate) and 0.5 mmol Ni²⁺ (Nickel nitrate hexahydrate) was dissolved in 5ml DI water. Then, 30 ml of 0.15M NaOH solution was added dropwise into the metal precursor solution with stirring and maintaining the pH >10. After two hour of co-precipitation reaction, the solution was

centrifuged and washed three times with deionized water and ethanol to collect the product. The collected product was vacuum dried at 60 °C overnight. The Ce doped samples were synthesized in the similar fashion by substituting 1, 5 and 10% Co²⁺ sites with Ce³⁺ (Cerium nitrate hexahydrate), the total metal precursors concentration is kept at 2 mM.

Electrochemical measurements

Electrochemical measurements were conducted in a typical three electrode cell configuration connected to a PalmSens4 potentiostat. All the measurements were recorded in 1M KOH electrolyte solution with glassy carbon working electrode coated with catalyst, graphite rod as counter and Ag/AgCl as a reference electrode. To prepare working electrode, first 3 mg of catalyst was dispersed in 300 µl DI water, 680 µl ethanol and 20 µl Nafion solution (5 wt%) and then the mixture was sonicated for 30 minutes to form a uniform dispersion. Then, 10 µl of catalyst dispersion was drop casted on the glassy carbon electrode and dried at room temperature before conducting electrochemical measurements. The mass loading on the working electrode was around 0.4 mg cm⁻², calculated through concentration and volume of the catalyst ink. All potentials were converted to RHE scale using the following equation:

$$E(\text{RHE}) = E(\text{Ag}/\text{AgCl}) + 0.059\text{pH} + 0.197$$

Whereas E represents the applied voltage on the working electrode. The potentials are reported as recorded without *iR* correction. All the electrochemical measurements were repeated 3 times to ensure the reliability.

Characterization

Scanning transmission electron microscopy coupled with energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (STEM-EDS) was performed on a JEOL JEM-F200 microscope operated at 200 kV. EDS data was analysed and processed using the Thermo Fisher Pathfinder X-ray Microanalysis Software. TEM specimens were prepared by suspending the particles in ethanol and drop casting onto carbon-coated copper grids.

AFM measurements were performed on the Bruker Dimension Icon SPM. Peak force tapping mode using the SCANASYST probe (from Bruker AFM probes) was used to perform the measurements. The scan size was initially set to 10µm in order to find the desired nanosheet, then a smaller scan size of 4µm was used to observe the sample at a higher resolution, finally the scan size was set to 1µm for an even higher resolution image. The scan rate was set to around 0.4 to 0.5Hz, and the imaging peak force was approximately 500 to 600pN. The feedback gain was adjusted accordingly to optimize tracking of the specimen surface, without any significant feedback noise. The resolution of the image was set to 512 pixels per line. AFM images were analysed using Gwyddion 2.55 software. UV-Vis absorption spectra of solid samples in reflectance mode was determined using Shimadzu UV 3600 UV-VIS-NIR spectrophotometer. The specific surface area was determined on a Micromeritics Tristar 3030 using the nitrogen porosimetry technique in conjunction with the Brunauer-Emmett-

Teller (BET) model. The samples were degassed at 80 °C for 3 h prior to analysis.

High-energy X-ray diffraction (HE-XRD) experiments were performed at the 11-ID-B beamline of the Advanced Photon Source (APS) using 86.7 keV X-rays. The HE-XRD patterns were background corrected, transformed into reduced structure factors, and Fourier transformed into atomic PDFs using the program PDFGetX3.⁶⁵ NEXAFS measurements were carried out at the O and N K-edges, and Ni, Co L₂/L₃-edges using the SXR beamline of the Australian Synchrotron. Samples were mounted on carbon tape for partial electron yield (PEY) detection. All the data were processed and analysed using QANT software.⁶⁶

In-situ electrochemical XAS measurements were performed at the 10-ID-B beamline of APS using the electrochemical cell shown in Figure S33. Catalyst inks were drop casted on carbon fiber paper and used as the working electrode, which was connected to the exterior of the cell via Ti wire. A graphite counter electrode and reference Ag/AgCl electrode were used to mimic a three-electrode cell experiment, where the XAS signal was collected in fluorescence mode. Co and Ni K-edge measurements were taken from ~200 eV below their respective K-edges (7.709 and 8.333 keV) to ~600 eV past Co K-edge and ~800 eV past Ni K-edge. Ce measurements were taken from ~200 eV below the L₃-edge (5.723 keV) up to ~430 eV past the edge. Each set of in-situ measurements was performed on a fresh sample. The Wavelet transformation analysis was performed using continuous Cauchy wavelet transformation (CCWT).⁶⁷ The resolution in k and R space can be controlled by the Cauchy parameter, *n* which was kept constant *n* = 200, such that for R values around 2 Å, the resolutions in the k and R spaces are, respectively, ΔR ± 0.1 Å and Δk ± 2.5 Å⁻¹. Artemis software⁶⁸ was used for the EXAFS modelling of the Co K-edges and Ni K-edges. Structure of trigonal LDH (P3m1) representing Ni²⁺ / Co²⁺ and “R -3 m:H” for Ni³⁺/Co³⁺ are used to generate the M-O and M-M paths. For Co K-edge EXAFS modelling was completed with both Co²⁺ and Co³⁺ phases. In modelling Ni K-edge data, Ni²⁺ phase was used in pristine, OCV and 1.22 V vs RHE samples while Ni³⁺ phase was used from 1.32, 1.52 and 1.62 V vs RHE samples. An amplitude reduction factor S₀² of 0.72 and 0.76 are used for Co and Ni K-edges respectively as determined by corresponding metal foils fit.

DFT calculations

We have carried out DFT calculations using the plane-wave Quantum Espresso code.⁶⁹ The core electrons were treated using the projector augmented wave method (PAW) method⁷⁰, and the Perdew-Burke-Ernzerhof (PBE) exchange-correlation functional⁷¹ was employed. The wavefunctions were expanded with a kinetic energy cut-off value of 35 Ry and appropriate k-grids were used. All relaxations proceeded until the residual forces on atoms were less than 0.03 eV/Å. DFT+U corrections are included for modelling the Co and Ce atoms, with *U* values of 3.5 and 5.0 eV, respectively. For modelling the (10 $\bar{1}$ 0) surface of γ-CoOOH, we have used a structure similar to the one reported in ref.⁷ for γ-NiOOH with intercalated K atoms.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information. This material is available free of charge via the Internet at <http://pubs.acs.org>.

Cyclic voltammetry curve, Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) analysis and equivalent circuit fitting, STEM image, EDX images, AFM images, UV-vis spectra, reciprocal Q-space HE-XRD patterns, crystallographic fitting of pair distribution patterns, BET plot, ex-situ soft X-ray XAS spectra before and after reaction, in-situ XAS spectra, WT analysis images, EXAFS fitting plots and results tables, in-situ XAS cell image, ECSA calculation and associated plots, large scale electrochemical stability and performance comparison, preparation of membrane electrode assemblies, Large scale electrochemical testing protocols.

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ACKNOWLEDGMENT

M.Z. acknowledges scholarship support from the Scientia Scholarship from UNSW. B. S. acknowledges scholarship support from the Research Training Program administered by the Department of Education of the Australian Government. HE-XRD and XAS experiments were carried out at the 11-ID-B and 10-ID-B beamlines of the Advanced Photon Source, a U.S. Department (DOE) Office of Science User Facility operated for the DOE Office of Science by Argonne National Laboratory under Contract No. DE-AC02-06CH11357. The 10-ID-B beamline is further supported by the Materials Research Collaborative Access Team and its member institutions. NEXAFS measurements were performed on the SXR beamline at the Australian Synchrotron, part of ANSTO, funded by the Australian Government. Part of this work was financially supported by the Bundesministerium für Bildung und Forschung (BMBF) under grant 03HY302Q (H2Mare - PTX - Wind) and under grant 03SF0613D (AEMready) and by the German Research Foundation (DFG) through grant reference number STR 596/12-1 (Paketantrag PAK 981). The project leading to this application has received funding by European Union's HORIZON.3.1 - The European Innovation Council (EIC) Program through the grant agreement 101071111 - ANEMEL. We acknowledge the facilities supported by Microscopy Australia at the Electron Microscope Unit and by the Mark Wainwright Analytical Centre at UNSW. We would like to thank Drs Leighanne Gallington and Joshua Wright for assistance at 11-ID-B and 10-ID-B respectively.

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An atomic scale electrocatalytic model supported by in-situ XAS and density functional theory is proposed to uncover the role of Ce dopant and oxygen vacancies in Co-Ni layered double hydroxides during oxygen evolution reaction (OER). The local structural model suggests pronounced conversion to OER reactive phase in Ce doped samples and promotion of oxygen vacancies through Ce redox $Ce^{3+} \leftrightarrow Ce^{4+}$ at oxidizing potentials.